

Modulating or ‘Transferring’ Between Non-octave Microtonal Scales

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses non-octave-based microtonal scales which can express a septimal minor triad formed by the 6th, 7th and 9th partials of the harmonic series. Three methods are proposed for modulating or transferring between each scale: by pivoting on common tones, building joint chords with pitches unique to each scale, or dynamically changing the sizes of generator and period to transform one scale into another. Motivation for this project was to shed light on two relatively unexplored possibilities in microtonality: scales without octaves, and multiple scales within a single piece of music. With today’s computers and synthesizers these areas can be explored more easily. The author borrows a goodness-of-fit strategy for a 6:7:9 chord and chooses three scales that divide the perfect fifth into 8, 13 and 18 equal steps. In addition to septimal triads other common tones are identified, e.g. a major seventh 1/6th-tone sharp, and the paper touches on less obvious manners of modulation. This project may be of interest to composers wishing to explore new facets of microtonality in their work.

1. INTRODUCTION

The conventional scale of twelve equal steps per octave is taken for granted in Western music. It is more economical to build instruments with 12 rather than 19, 31, 43 or 55 keys. Scales of these many notes can approximate the historical temperaments of 1/3rd-, 1/4-, 1/5th and 1/6th-comma meantone, respectively. By slightly shrinking the perfect fifth they offer thirds and sixths that are better in tune than our 12-tone variety.

Prooijen and Carlos, however, showed that by abandoning the octave and shrinking the semitone from 100 to 78 cents or smaller, one can obtain major and minor triads that are closer to being pure [1, p. 51][2]. But what of other triads? And what happens when we lose the octave and its ability to invert or transpose chords by an interval of equivalency? Intervals other than 2/1 are possible yet delicate such as Bohlen–Pierce’s 3/1 [3][4] or, theoretically, Moreno’s 5/1 and higher [5].

As for contemporary music and theory based around the 3/2 perfect fifth one could look at compositions by Car-

los¹ and Serafini [6], or the much older traditional music of Georgia [7, p. 830] and the Eastern Arctic region of Canada [8].

My current work-in-progress, *Apollo*, for percussion and computer, uses three scales that divide the fifth into equal steps but does not presently use the fifth as interval of equivalency for motivic transposition. A previous work, *Bird of Janus*, for Bohlen–Pierce (BP) clarinet, was written in both the BP and Carlos alpha scales² and appropriates a common tone of 1170 cents as interval of equivalency. For the new composition strategies other than the use of common tones were desired for moving from one type of tuning to another.

Computer code in Matlab and Max/MSP assisted me in composing music which could dynamically modulate or ‘transfer’, to use Darreg’s preferred term, between multiple microtonal scales. The impetus came from Wolf’s *transitional fifth-squashing* [9] and from *dynamic tuning* by Milne, Sethares and Plamondon [10].

The scales had to satisfy the following criteria: they must (1) be able to express a septimal minor triad with minimal error, (2) have equally-spaced steps (3) which are not ‘too small’, and (4) not contain an octave. I then considered three strategies for transferring between these scales and presently named them: (1) *communic*, (2) *interharmonic*, and (3) *dynacyclic*. At the risk of sounding whimsical these terms are concise and defined in section 2.2.

2. METHODS

Chords shall be expressed as frequency ratios, e.g. 4:5:6 major triad; dyads or intervals either as ratios, e.g. 5/4 major third and 3/2 perfect fifth; or as intervals from a scale, e.g. 4\12 and 7\12 (note the backslash); scales as either steps per interval, e.g. 12ed2 meaning 12 equal divisions of the 2/1 octave; or as size of scale step in cents, e.g. 100c for the standard semitone with frequency ratio equal to the 12th root of 2.

2.1 Approximating

Prooijen approximated the 4:5:6 major triad with the use of continued fractions to express the answer to equation 1, where f , g and h equal 4, 5 and 6, respectively. Although he found a value of 78.0c Carlos arrived at the same answer a few years later by plotting the results of a goodness-of-fit algorithm using non-integer divisions of the octave, and named this same scale *alpha*, as it is known today.

¹ The title track from her album *Beauty in the Beast* alternates between 9 and 11 equal divisions of the perfect fifth.

² 13ed3/1 and 9ed3/2, about 146.3 and 78.0 cents.

$$\frac{h}{f} \log \frac{g}{f} \quad (1)$$

Both Prooijen's and Carlos's methods were applied to a 6:7:9 septimal triad. This triad was chosen because it is the next possible triad in the harmonic series, after 4:5:6, which contains a perfect fifth and which is not playable in the standard 12ed2 scale [11]. This approach yielded three candidate scales and their step sizes were fine-tuned using Benson's formula (eq. 2) for minimizing the mean square deviation from the ideal interval ratios [12, p. 222]. Step size in cents is represented by s while a , b and c represent the number of steps to reach the perfect fifth, septimal major third and septimal minor third:

$$s = 1200 \times \frac{a \log_2 \frac{3}{2} + b \log_2 \frac{9}{7} + c \log_2 \frac{7}{6}}{a^2 + b^2 + c^2} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Transferring

Pivot tones between scales were found by simply comparing pitch values and noting correspondences when their differences were less than ten cents. This may be called a *communic* strategy, to be used either melodically or harmonically as common notes or chords.

To identify harmonic potential within and between scales Matlab was programmed to perform a multi-dimensional search and compare all possible ratios with each scale degree of any given scale. The user must specify a prime limit,³ a subset thereof, e.g. [2 3 7], or even a set of fractions such as [7/6 3/2]. The user may also stipulate a tolerance for inaccuracy such as 10 cents as well as a maximum *harmonic distance* (eq. 3) [13].

$$HD(f_a, f_b) \propto \log(a) + \log(b) = \log(ab) \quad (3)$$

The output may be used to build a multi-dimensional lattice or Tonnetz for visualizing harmonic structure in the scale (q.v. Johnston, Tenney or Vogel). Such structures could show all scales' pitches, their common pitches, or just their unique pitches.

The latter is the concept behind the *interharmonic* strategy for transferring between scales. To illustrate, imagine scale X to be (0 2 4 6 8 10 12) semitones and scale Y as (0 3 6 9 12)—in other words a whole-tone scale and a diminished seventh chord. Neither scale can play a three-note semitone cluster without assistance from the other, i.e. (2 3 4) or (8 9 10) would require two notes from X and one from Y . The semitone cluster, then, could function as a motivic sonority that signals harmonic transition from one scale to the other. This method is applicable to conventional 12ed2 tuning or between radically different microtonal scales.

For this paper the third strategy will be called *dynacyclic*, however, proper credit is due to Wolf and Milne et al. whose work inspired this project. Wolf in particular was interested in modulating between the Western chromatic scale and an approximation of a Javanese *pelog* scale, as well as in hybridizing them. By casting their differing sizes

³ A prime limit is the set of all prime numbers up to a given number, e.g. prime limit 7 is [2 3 5 7].

of fifths as generators and the octave as a period he could morph from one scale to the other by gradually shrinking the fifth from 720 to 700, 685 then 667 cents. This has the effect of pitches splitting apart from a 5ed2 (anhemitonic pentatonic) scale, fanning outward to form a 12ed2 scale, folding inward and colliding into a 7ed2 (anhemitonic heptatonic) scale, expanding out again into 9ed2 and so on.

In section 3.2.3 this technique was adopted as a method for transitioning between non-octave microtonal scales. Coincidentally Wolf was also interested in octave-based scales generated by sequences of tempered 7/6 thirds instead of tempered 3/2 fifths, whereas this paper is focused on fifth-based scales generated by sequences of tempered 7/6 or 9/7 thirds, as will be explained next.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Approximating 6:7:9

3.1.1 Continued fractions

Letting f , g and h be 6:7:9 in equation 1 resulted in 0.38018 which, when represented as a continued fraction in abbreviated notation, is [0; 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, ...]. The first four terms were rejected since they indicate 'scales' with a large margin of error. The next three terms rationalized to the convergents 3\8, 8\21 and 19\50,⁴ suggesting scales which divide the 3/2 perfect fifth into 8, 21 and 50 equal steps, with the 7/6 ratio occurring on the third, eighth and nineteenth intervals of each.

Only the 8ed3/2 scale was kept, however, since 21ed3/2 is simply the 1/6th-tone scale, i.e. one which contains an octave, and a 50ed3/2 scale would have had a step size of 14 cents which is too small for this project.

The semi-convergents [0; 2, 1, 1, 1, 1] and [0; 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1] resulted in 5\13 and 11\29. The 13ed3/2 scale was kept and the 29ed3/2 scale was considered but then rejected for its small step size of 24 cents.

3.1.2 Goodness-of-fit

Figure 1. Peaks indicate scales which approximate the ratios 7/6, 9/7 and 3/2.

⁴ Read as "3 of 8 (divisions)" etc.

A variation on Carlos's plot of error across step size was used. On the x-axis are non-integer divisions of the 3/2 perfect fifth instead of 2/1 octave, and the y-axis shows accuracy by root-mean-square instead of sum-of-squares. Figure 4 shows strong peaks at 8, 13, 16, 18 and 21ed3/2. In addition to those divisions already found in section 3.1.1 the plot indicates 16ed3/2 and perhaps 18ed3/2. The former is merely a doubling of 8ed3/2 and the latter, though not as accurate, is 'not too bad' and was therefore retained.

In summary three non-octave scales which could approximate a 6:7:9 septimal minor triad were chosen: 8, 13, and 18 equal divisions of 3/2. Finding the interval for 7/6 in the last scale was easily done with equation 4.

$$\frac{18}{\log \frac{3}{2}} \times \log \frac{7}{6} \approx 7 \quad (4)$$

3.1.3 Minimizing deviation

Finally, using Benson's formula (eq. 2) the fifths of each scale were tweaked about one cent in order to minimize inaccuracies for all three intervals in a 6:7:9 triad. For the 8, 13 and 18ed3/2 scales the final step sizes became 87.670, 54.033 and 39.047 cents, respectively.

3.2 Transferring or modulating

3.2.1 Communic

Common tones between scales are the septimal thirds and perfect fifth. Although the 3/2 fifths were perceptually identical the septimal thirds did not fare as well. The most noticeable bump might be heard between 8ed3/2 and 18ed3/2 where the 9/7 major third differs by 8.8 cents or where the 7/6 minor third differs by 10.3 cents.

When comparing scales up to their intervals nearest the octave another common tone of around 1136c was discovered—a major seventh 1/6th-tone sharp. Other affinities are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Common pitches between scales. Numerals indicate cents' deviation from standard notation.

Figure 2 shows common pitches which differ by seven cents or less between scales, from 8 to 13 to 18 divisions per fifth, then back to 8. The root, C4, is consistent and

the perfect fifth, G4, hardly wavers at all. The 7/6 interval in between is shown as D#4 about a 1/3rd-tone flat but was too jarring between 18 and 8ed3/2, in the last system, to be considered as a common tone. Surprisingly a very smooth transition between 8 and 18 ed3/2 is possible using a 'neutral third-neutral seventh' chord, as seen in the bottom system.

Additional pivot tones would be available by tolerating more cents' difference or by looking for correlations beyond the quasi-octaves presented.

3.2.2 Interharmonic

The idea was to find not only tones that were common between scales but harmonic structures that could only be possible across simultaneous scale systems. This is complicated but manageable with computation. A cursory search for chords between the 8 and 13 ed3/2 scales reveals two near-perfect versions of the most familiar chords: a just intonation version of an equal-tempered minor triad, 16:19:24, and a nearly perfect equal-tempered major triad. The latter can also be extended to a major seventh chord. Figure 3 shows how the scale pitches complement one another to build these sonorities which are not possible in either scale alone.

Figure 3. Unique pitches between scales which form chords. Numerals indicate cents' deviation from standard notation.

The top staff is in 13ed3/2 tuning and the bottom in 8ed3/2, and the 'tonic' of both keys is C4. The first measure is a minor triad where the root and fifth come from the 1st and 14th intervals of 13ed3/2, and the third comes from the 4th interval of 8ed3/2. The second measure is a major seventh chord where the root and fifth come from the 1st and 9th intervals of 8ed3/2, and the third and seventh come from the 9th and 22nd intervals of 13ed3/2. These two chords are exceptionally accurate and by loosening the tolerance for cents' deviation many more joint-chords can be constructed.

3.2.3 Dynacyclic

Figure 4 attempts to show what happens when scales are created using a generator of 9/7 and a period of 3/2, although with the tweaked step sizes listed in section 3.1.3. From left to right the scales change over time as the generator is increased from 429.5 to 432.3 then 438.4 cents, and the period is slightly decreased from 702.8 to 702.4 then 701.4 cents. Although these changes might seem minute the differences add up after subsequent generations.

Figure 4. Each circle represents a perfect fifth, where dots are notes from each scale, coloured for ease of locating in the figure. Dotted in-ticks indicate standard semitones for reference, i.e. seven ticks per fifth. Arrows show narrowing intervals which vanish in the next scale (and can be imagined on the other short arc lengths around each circle).

When plotted around a ring, generations 13 to 17 move more quickly than 8 to 12. This can be seen in the figure as the black dots cover the blue dots, and the red dots cover both the black and blue dots. Table 1 summarizes how the 18ed scale twists into a 13ed scale. One can see that five pitches have folded onto five others to form unison pairs:

Ratio	Interval	Size	Generation(s)
1/1	0		0, 13
	1	54c	5
	2		10
	3		2, 15
	4		7
7/6	5	270c	12
	6		4, 17
	7		9
9/7	8	432c	1, 14
	9		6
	10		11
	11		3, 16
	12		8

Table 1. 13ed3/2 scale: intervals (left) and generations of 9/7 (right).

When the process is continued, as from 13ed to 8ed, five more notes fold onto unisons resulting in six pairs and two triplets of 9/7 generations.

Ratio	Interval	Size	Generation(s)
1/1	0		0, 8, 16
	1	88c	5, 13
	2		2, 10
7/6	3	263c	7, 15
	4		4, 12
9/7	5	438c	1, 9, 17
	6		6, 14
	7		3, 11

Table 2. 8ed3/2 scale: intervals (left) and generations of 9/7 (right).

4. DISCUSSION

Microtonal music and research typically assumes that the octave remains in place as interval of equivalency. Had I wanted to consider octave-based scales, instead of non-octave scales, which can express a septimal triad then the following would have been good choices (in order from okay to best): 27, 39, 31, 22, 41, and 36 equal divisions of the octave. The last three are especially good but the sixth-tone scale (36ed2) is practically perfect.

Non-octave scales offer relatively unexplored harmonic territory. Indeed two of the three choices discussed in this paper are already well documented: 8ed3/2 is essentially Morrison's 88c scale, and 18ed3/2 is better known as Carlos's *alpha prime*.

4.1 Comparison to other scales

The Scala archive is a compendium of over four thousand scales, each comprising a short description and a list of intervals in cents and or ratios. Many are historical temperaments or interpretations of cultural scales, and many others are artistic or academic expressions of tuning concepts.

For example, the archive contains eight scales in the 8ed3/2 family from between 1998–2011. Morrison himself includes scales of 88 cents or slightly less, e.g. least-squares and minimax solutions for approximating intervals 11/9, 10/7 and 7/4 in addition to those intervals in the 6:7:9 triad. With the exception of McLaren's '38th root of 7' they are all excellent choices for expressing the 6:7:9 triad.

There is a half dozen which would belong to the family of what I am calling 13ed3/2, from 1996 to 2007. The thirteenth root of 3/2 or my adjustment is clearly best, and the next closest might be the '62nd root of 7' or '35th root of 3' scale.

Finally there are also eight scales within the 18ed3/2 family of around 39 cent steps from 1996–2007, however the next best option after alpha prime for approximating the 6:7:9 triad would be the '15th root of 7/5' scale, though not a close choice.⁵

The septimal triad could be extended to include the major seventh seen earlier, interpreted as either 27/14 in 7-limit harmony or as 25/13 in 13-limit. This would of course

⁵ <http://www.huygens-fokker.org/docs/scalesdir.txt>, accessed 28 April 2016.

influence the ideal size of scale step and quite likely alter the details of all aspects so far examined.

5. CONCLUSIONS

These scales promise interesting harmonies in and of themselves but modulating or moving in between seems to be a worthy challenge. In the words of Darreg: "Suppose one deliberately composes something which changes tuning-systems in the middle or at several places. It would seem inadvisable to extend the meaning of the already-overburdened word 'modulation' to this novel and startling effect. Hence, *transfer*." [14]

Leveraging pitches that are common to two or more scales is an obvious and effective method for transferring from one scale or tuning to another. The opposite approach, of using pitches distinct to each scale for building joint sonorities, is another avenue worth pursuing. The example introduced in fig. 3 is admittedly small and could be developed further. Finally the technique of dynamic tuning is getting attention, especially as it naturally goes hand in hand with dynamic timbre matching as explained by Sethares, Milne et al.; of adjusting the overtone structure of a (synthesized) instrument in real-time to "mediate sensory dissonance" of any given scale's interval properties [15][16], or by stretching the timbre such that the partials are no longer integer multiples of a fundamental. This certainly makes sense with alpha prime which could easily pass as a 31-tone scale having a stretched octave of 1210.5 cents.

This paper presented examples of non-octave scales that could express a septimal minor triad but of course the techniques can be applied to other harmonies. And although there seems to have already been a push in the early 1990s for microtonal research, judging by the literature, it is this author's hope that the ideas presented here may inspire composers to reconsider microtonality, especially with the ability of today's technology to smoothly transition from any scale system to another, with or without octaves.

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6. REFERENCES

- [1] K. v. Prooijen, "A theory of equal-tempered scales," *Interface*, vol. 7, pp. 45–56, 1978.
- [2] W. Carlos, "Tuning: At the crossroads," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 29–43, 1987.
- [3] H. Bohlen, "13 tonstufen in der duodezime," *Acustica*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 76–86, 1978.
- [4] M. Mathews, L. A. Roberts, and J. R. Pierce, "Four new scales based on nonsuccessive-integer-ratio chords," *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 75, p. S10, 1984.
- [5] E. Moreno, *Expanded Tunings in Contemporary Music: Theoretical Innovations and Practical Applications*, ser. Studies in the History and Interpretation of Music. Lewiston; Queenston; Lampeter: The Edwin Mellen Press, 1992, vol. 30.
- [6] C. Serafini. (2002–16) Carlo Serafini: Futurist composer. [Online]. Available: <http://www.seraph.it>
- [7] J. Jordania, *The Garland Encyclopedia of World Music*. New York and London: Garland Publishing, Inc., 2000, vol. 8 Europe, ch. Georgia, pp. 826–849.
- [8] N. Beaudry, *The Garland Encyclopedia of World Music*. New York and London: Garland Publishing, Inc., 2001, vol. 3 The United States and Canada, ch. Arctic Canada and Alaska, pp. 374–382.
- [9] D. Wolf, "Why ratios are a good/bad model of intonation," in *The Ratio book: a documentation of The Ratio Symposium, Royal Conservatory, The Hague, 14–16 December 1992*, ser. Feedback Papers, C. Barlow, Ed., vol. 43. Cologne: Royal Conservatory The Hague, 1999, pp. 160–175.
- [10] A. Milne, W. Sethares, and J. Plamondon, "Isomorphic controllers and dynamic tuning: Invariant fingering over a tuning continuum," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 15–32, Dec. 2007. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1162/comj.2007.31.4.15>
- [11] A. Honingh, "Measures of consonance in a goodness-of-fit model for equal-tempered scales," In Proc. International Computer Music Conference, Tech. Rep., 2003.
- [12] D. Benson, *Music: A Mathematical Offering*. Cambridge University Press, 2008.
- [13] J. Tenney, *Soundings 13: The Music of James Tenney*. Frog Peak, 1984, ch. John Cage and the Theory of Harmony.
- [14] I. Darreg. (1990) Transfer. [Online]. Available: <http://www.tonalsoft.com/sonic-arts/darreg/transfer.htm>
- [15] A. J. Milne, M. Carlé, W. A. Sethares, T. Noll, and S. Holland, *Scratching the Scale Labyrinth*. Springer, 2011.
- [16] W. A. Sethares, *Tuning, Timbre, Spectrum, Scale*, 2nd ed. London: Springer, 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://www.springer.com/engineering/book/978-1-85233-797-1>